

pH-metric Study of Bivalent Metal Chelates using D(+)-Saccharic Acid as Secondary Ligand

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Velasco *et al.*¹ reported the stability constants for the anionic complexes of D(+)-saccharic acid of the type, $(\text{CuLH}_3)^-$, $(\text{NiLH}_3)^-$, $(\text{CoLH}_3)^-$ and $\text{Mn}(\text{LH}_3)^-$, where $\text{LH}_6 = \text{D}(+)\text{-saccharic acid}$. They also reported $1 : 2 [\text{Cu}(\text{LH}_4)_2]^{2-}$ and its polynuclear species. Beneitez and Millan² studied the composition and stability constant of $1 : 1 \text{ Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-D}(+)\text{-saccharic acid}$ complex. Mai³ reported the dissociation constants of D(+)-saccharic acid. Macarovic⁴ made a potentiometric study of the complexes of D(+)-saccharic acid with Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} . Spacu *et al.*⁵ studied the conditions under which some lanthanide compounds were formed with saccharic acid. Any systematic study on the coordinating tendency of this acid has been limited despite the advantages that it may offer for coordination with metal ions due to the availability of six potential coordinating sites (four hydroxyl and two carboxylic acid groups) in its structure.

The present potentiometric study reports the formation constants of the $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA-Sa}$ complexes, where disodium salt of EDTA has been used as primary ligand (A) and D(+)-saccharic acid, H_2Sa , as secondary ligand (L) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and at 0.1 M ionic strength (NaClO_4).

Results and Discussion

The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL for the M-L, binary systems were obtained by standard expressions⁶. The formation curves corresponding to the proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria were obtained by plotting \bar{n}_A and \bar{n} against pH and pL respectively. The $\text{p}K_1^{\text{H}}$ and $\text{p}K_2^{\text{H}}$ values of D(+)-saccharic acid were obtained by the usual Irving-Rossotti technique. The K_1^{H} and K_2^{H} values were found to be 7.413×10^{-4} and 5.754×10^{-5} respectively, which were close to the literature values 7.25×10^{-4} and 7.95×10^{-5} (Ref. 1) and 9.78×10^{-4} and 11.55×10^{-5} (Ref. 3). The metal-ligand stability constants ($\log K_1$) for the $1 : 1 \text{ M-L}$ binary complexes were similarly evaluated by various computational methods.

The $\log K_1$ values obtained by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n} values were found to be 3.86 ± 0.07 , 3.70 ± 0.06 , 3.65 ± 0.06 , 3.56 ± 0.03 and 3.46 ± 0.03 for the Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} systems respectively. In the case of $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{-Sa}$ and $\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA-Sa}$ systems in the alkaline range, the colour of the solution gradually changed from almost colourless to red. This may be due to partial oxidation of Mn^{II} by molecular oxygen⁷. Since the present pH-titra-

tions were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere, the oxidation of Mn^{II} may be due to the presence of dissolved oxygen in the solutions employed.

For the formation of ternary complexes (MAL) the necessary conditions like the formation of primary ligand complex, MA at low pH and its stability at higher pH at which the combination of the secondary ligand with MA takes place, were satisfied by choosing the secondary ligand (L) in such a way that the stability of the ML complex was much less than that of the primary complex, MA. Thus the possibility of the ligand displacement of the following type was excluded. $\text{MA} + \text{L} \rightleftharpoons \text{ML} + \text{A}$. The formation of the mixed ligand complex in the present system was therefore assumed to take place in two distinctly separate steps,

$$\text{and } K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}} = \frac{[\text{MAL}]}{[\text{MA}][\text{L}]}$$

charges are omitted. The species present in solution were therefore MA and MAL. The possibility of the formation of other species like MA_2 and ML_2 were excluded. However, there may also occur hydrolysis of MA and even of

Fig. 1. pH-metric titration curves of $1 : 1 : 1 \text{ Ni}^{\text{II}}\text{-EDTA-D}(+)\text{-saccharic acid}$ system at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ and 0.1 M ionic strength (NaClO_4): (A) HClO_4 , (B) $\text{HClO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{Sa}$, (C) $\text{HClO}_4 + \text{EDTA} + \text{NiSO}_4$ and (D) $\text{HClO}_4 + \text{EDTA} + \text{NiSO}_4 + \text{H}_2\text{Sa}$.

M(II). In the presence of a multidentate ligand like D(+)-saccharic acid, the complex MAL was assumed to be formed in preference of MA(OH)_n. In dilute solution, it was also presumed that the polynuclear species do not exist⁸.

The values of \bar{n}_{mix} , the average number of secondary ligands attached to the primary complex MA, were calculated by an extension of Irving-Rossotti technique at different pH values from the horizontal distance ($V_4 - V_3$) - ($V_2 - V_1$) in the same pH axis where V_1 , V_2 , V_3 and V_4 are the volumes of sodium hydroxide required to reach the same pH in curves A, B, C and D respectively (Fig. 1). The values of \bar{n}_{mix} and the free ligand exponent, PL_{mix} in the mixed ligand systems were calculated by the standard expressions¹⁰. The plots of $\bar{n}_{\text{mix}}/L_{\text{mix}}$ vs L_{mix} in the above M(II)-EDTA-Sa systems were found to be smooth curves (figure not shown). This also suggests the absence of polynuclear and protonated species⁹. The values of \bar{n}_{mix} did not exceed 0.5 in the \bar{n}_{mix} scale and hence the formation constants ($\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$) were calculated by the method of interpolation at various \bar{n}_{mix} values. The values of the formation constants thus obtained were found to be 3.60 ± 0.08 , 3.39 ± 0.09 , 3.33 ± 0.08 , 3.26 ± 0.10 and 3.21 ± 0.08 for the Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Mn^{II} and Zn^{II} systems respectively.

The values of stability constants of the ML complexes were found to be higher than those of the MAL complexes. The cause of this has been ascribed to the coulombic repulsion between the binary complex (M-EDTA)²⁻ and the incoming ligand, Sa²⁻ as shown by the reactions,

EDTA being a hexadentate ligand formed a very stable chelate occupying six coordination sites. Accommodation of another polydentate ligand leading to the formation of a ternary complex would therefore create an extra strain on the ternary complex and count for the lowering in the values of stability constant. The order of stability of the ternary complexes was found to be, Zn^{II} < Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II}. This obeys Irving-Williams natural order¹².

Experimental

All chemical used were of A.R. grade. D(+)-saccharic acid was derived from insoluble D(+)-calcium saccharate

(Sigma) by ion-exchange method¹³.

For the study of ML, binary complexes the following three solutions were prepared : (a) 0.05 M HClO₄, (b) 0.05 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M H₂Sa and (c) 0.05 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M H₂Sa + 0.005 M NiSO₄. For the study of MAL, ternary complexes, the following four solutions were prepared as per the method followed earlier^{10,11} : (A) 0.05 M HClO₄, (B) 0.05 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M H₂Sa, (C) 0.05 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M NiSO₄ + 0.005 M EDTA and (D) 0.05 M HClO₄ + 0.005 M NiSO₄ + 0.005 M EDTA + 0.005 M H₂Sa. The initial volume in each case was kept at 50 ml by the addition of suitable volume of distilled water and the ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 M by the addition of suitable amount of neutral sodium perchlorate solution. pH-metric titrations were carried out in N₂-atmosphere with a pH-meter model ECIL-5652 at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ using carbonate-free NaOH solution. The carbonate content of sodium hydroxide was assessed¹⁴. Each titration was repeated to get reproducible result.

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